

Explaining the Optimization of Dynamic Tariffs for Electric Vehicles Charging with Large Language Models

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Abstract—The electrification of transport is accelerating the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) and increasing the need for smart charging strategies. Dynamic tariffs can unlock EV flexibility by incentivizing charging during periods of lower carbon intensity or reduced grid congestion. However, the optimization models used to design such tariffs are often complex and opaque, limiting transparency, trust, and practical adoption. This work proposes a large language model (LLM)-guided evolutionary framework based on verbal reinforcement learning to generate interpretable surrogate models for the EV tariffs optimization problem via imitation learning. By combining LLM-driven rule generation with multi-objective selection, the proposed approach balances imitation accuracy with structural interpretability. The resulting rule-based models closely approximate the outputs of the original optimization problems while remaining compact and human-interpretable, achieving competitive performance relative to standard machine learning baselines. These results highlight the potential of LLMs to extract interpretable representations from conventional mathematical optimization models, which are often perceived as “black-box” by human decision-makers.

Index Terms—electric vehicle, smart charging, dynamic tariffs, large language models, interpretability, imitation learning

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, electric vehicles (EVs) have seen rapid adoption, with over 17 million units sold worldwide in 2024, a 25% increase from 2023 and representing 20% of total car sales. Under current policies, this share is projected to reach 40% by 2030 [1]. However, this rapid integration of EVs into mobility entails different challenges. The increase in electricity demand, if left uncontrolled, could cause considerable stress upon the electrical grid [2]. Different strategies are available to tackle this issue. For instance, direct smart charging dynamically adjusts charging processes based on real-time grid conditions, while indirectly controlled charging uses price or incentive signals to encourage behavioral change

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among EV drivers. Essentially, it aims to shift demand to off-peak periods through dynamic pricing strategies, therefore acting as a demand response mechanism [3]. Dynamic pricing techniques include (a) time-of-use tariffs, which use fixed rates for peak and off-peak hours or (b) real-time dynamic tariffs, which resort to current grid conditions to form price signals aiming to influence behavior in the benefit of the power grid.

Across literature, dynamic pricing for EV charging has been explored from multiple perspectives. Kazemtarghi et al. [4] address congestion management through a scenario-based stochastic formulation that models EV charging station choice as a function of price, distance, and other factors, thereby redistributing charging demand and improving station utilization. In the context of distributed energy resources (DERs), Alanazi et al. [5] propose a stochastic transactive framework for EV parking lots with PV and battery storage, whereas Vashisth et al. [6] design flat and dynamic tariffs for fast-charging stations with DERs while explicitly capturing user response through a price-cum-convenience elasticity model. For low-carbon charging, Silva et al. [7] develop a chance-constrained stochastic tariff design under uncertainty in load, renewables, and grid carbon intensity, complemented by a price elasticity matrix to capture how EV demand shifts across time in response to dynamic tariffs, while Li et al. [8] combine time-of-use pricing with marginal emission factors in a multi-objective smart charging strategy.

While these models work in theory, an additional challenge for their real-world deployment is the lack of interpretability of the mathematical optimization models [9] used to design the tariffs. This issue obscures the relationship between inputs and the optimization model’s outputs, posing a challenge analogous to the lack of explainability in machine learning (ML) models, and motivating the development of similar interpretability approaches for operations research problems [10]. The inherent complexity of these pricing models, particularly under stochastic formulations, can ultimately discourage EV charging station (EVCS) operators and drivers from adopting them. Silva et al. [7] partially address this challenge by approximating the behavior of their optimization model using a

surrogate tree-based ML model and an explainability analysis based on Shapley values.

Recent advances in large language models (LLMs) have demonstrated their potential across several dimensions. First, they enable automation of optimization and decision-making through frameworks that translate natural language problems into mathematical optimization models and solver code [11], LLM-enhanced feature engineering for forecasting [12], iterative optimization via meta-prompts [13], and the automated design of heuristics for NP-hard problems using reflective evolution [14]. Second, they contribute to improve explainability and human-AI collaboration, for instance, through interactive optimization explanations [15], their usage as “devil’s advocates” to challenge explainable AI outputs [16], and the generation of logic rules in healthcare settings [17]. Third, they show potential in the electricity sector for tasks such as forecasting, diagnostics and document analysis, while also facing current limitations in safety and domain adaptation [18].

This work proposes an LLM-guided evolutionary framework to learn interpretable surrogate models for dynamic EV charging tariffs produced by a chance-constrained stochastic optimization problem. Rather than improving the original optimization framework, the goal is to make its tariff-setting decisions transparent and auditable. The main contributions are: (a) an LLM-based, novel feedback-driven evolutionary rule generation mechanism that discovers compact symbolic models able to approximate the optimizer’s tariff outputs with high imitation accuracy; and (b) a natural-language explanation layer that translates the learned rules into stakeholder-oriented descriptions while preserving fidelity to the underlying symbolic logic.

II. METHODOLOGY FOR AUGMENTED INTERPRETABILITY

A. Overview

The proposed methodology combines LLM-guided rule generation with numerical optimization to derive interpretable surrogate models (imitation learning) for an EV tariff stochastic optimization model. The framework alternates between generating rule structures in a general-purpose programming language (Python in this case) and optimizing their numerical parameters. Two LLM instances support this process: one proposes candidate rule structures (LLM-RG), while the other provides feedback to guide their refinement (LLM-FB). Candidate solutions are evaluated according to predictive performance and structural complexity, enabling the search to identify rules that balance performance and interpretability. An overview of the methodology is depicted in Fig. 1.

Once the new Python code structure is generated, a covariance matrix adaptation evolution strategy (CMA-ES) optimizes the thresholds to minimize the imitation error. At the core of the evolutionary cycle is a multi-objective selection mechanism based on the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II), an algorithm that evaluates candidate rules with respect to two competing goals: minimizing mean absolute error (MAE) and minimizing structural complexity. This approach enables the algorithm to naturally converge

towards solutions that offer an effective balance between imitation accuracy and interpretability.

B. Dataset Generation and Processing

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the methodology starts with dataset generation, which in this context is derived from a stochastic optimization model for setting dynamic EV tariffs. The optimization model proposed in [7] for dynamic carbon-aware EV charging tariffs is used to generate a dataset comprising more than 14,000 samples obtained by solving the optimization problem, with 21 variables in total. These include price elasticity of demand; calendar variables (e.g., hour of the day); summary statistics: namely the mean, interquartile range, and coefficient of variation of day-ahead forecasts (EVCS load in kW , renewable energy supply in kW , and grid carbon intensity in g_{CO_2}/kWh); and additional variables such as day-ahead spot prices ($\text{€}/kWh$) and the daily carbon emissions budget (g_{CO_2}). The target variable corresponds to the optimal EV charging tariff ($\text{€}/kWh$) resulting from the optimization problem, which ranges from 0.05 to 0.6 $\text{€}/kWh$. Given the dataset size, only summary statistics were provided to the LLMs, specifically the *min*, *max*, and mean values of each feature.

C. Characterization of Candidate Solutions

Let $\mathcal{D} = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ be the tabular dataset described in Section II-B, where N is the number of instances, $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is a feature vector, and $y_i \in \mathbb{R}$ is the target variable. The primary goal is to find a candidate solution $f_\theta : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, provided by the LLM-RG and expressed as a Python code, that achieves low imitation error, assessed through the MAE while remaining structurally simple, quantified by an abstract syntax tree (AST)-based structural complexity score.

The structural skeleton of a candidate solution consists of a set of *if/else* conditions and arithmetic operations over the dataset features.

Inspired by prior work on mental-operation-based assessment [19], the complexity of a candidate solution is measured by parsing the generated Python rule into an AST and computing $\mathcal{C}(f_\theta)$ from counts of selected AST node types according to the penalties defined in Table I. This provides a simple proxy for structural complexity.

Table I: Weights used in the AST-based structural complexity score.

AST Node / Operation	Weight
<i>if</i> statement (condition check and branch overhead)	+2
Comparison operator	+1
Binary arithmetic operator (+, −, ×, ÷)	+1
Boolean operator connection (e.g., <i>and/or</i>)	+1
Function call (e.g., <i>max</i> , <i>min</i>)	+1
Variable assignment	+1
<i>return</i> statement	+1

Note that an *if/elif* node receives weight +2 because, beyond evaluating the comparison itself, the reader must also follow a branch and keep alternative paths in mind. All

Figure 1: Overview of the evolutionary LLM-based rule generator methodology.

binary arithmetic operators receive the same weight because the metric is intended as a simple structural proxy and does not aim to model fine-grained cognitive differences between arithmetic operations. Moreover, the same scoring procedure is applied consistently to all evolved rules and baseline models.

Finally, a lower $\mathcal{C}(f_\theta)$ indicates a structurally simpler and more easily inspectable candidate solution, which can be compared with widely used predictive models for benchmarking.

D. Evolutionary Learning

The proposed algorithm follows an evolutionary loop in which the LLM acts as a mutation operator over symbolic rule structures. Starting from an initial population generated by LLM-RG, each generation preserves the global elite (and selected survivors) and produces offspring through feedback-guided mutation. Periodically, numerical literals are optimized every N_{opt} generations. In turn, the framework performs multi-objective survivor selection based on MAE and structural complexity.

Algorithm 1 summarizes the overall procedure. Offspring generation is implemented through two LLM calls: LLM-FB proposes mutation actions (Table II), and LLM-RG synthesizes the revised Python rule. Details on the prompts are available in a dedicated repository [20]. To reduce computational cost, intermediate numerical optimizations can be performed on a random subsample of size $\alpha \cdot N$, while MAE reporting for individuals is computed on the full dataset. Survivor selection follows NSGA-II, a multi-objective evolutionary method based on non-dominated sorting and crowding distance, in the $(\text{MAE}, \mathcal{C})$ space, with structural duplicate removal used to preserve diversity. At the end of the run, the best individual can be further refined with a final optimization on the full data.

Table II: Mutation action space for the LLM-FB.

Action type	Description
add_branch	Insert a new conditional branch
prune_branch	Remove a redundant branch
merge_branches	Combine overlapping conditions
simplify_condition	Reduce condition complexity
add_remove_feature	Introduce or drop a feature
replace_feature	Substitute one feature for another
add_remove_interaction	Add or remove a feature product term
reorder_conditions	Change branching priority
linearize_branch	Replace a branch with a linear expression

Algorithm 1 LLM-guided evolutionary learning

Require: Dataset $D = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, population size μ , generations G , optimization frequency N_{opt} , optimization subsample fraction α

Ensure: Best rule f^*

- 1: Initialize population $P^{(0)}$ with μ rules generated by LLM-RG
- 2: Evaluate all candidates on the full dataset using MAE and structural complexity \mathcal{C}
- 3: Set global best solution f^*
- 4: Select survivors with NSGA-II in $(\text{MAE}, \mathcal{C})$
- 5: **for** $g = 1$ to G **do**
- 6: Reproduce population from elite/survivors using LLM-FB (mutation actions) and LLM-RG (revised code)
- 7: Evaluate offspring on the full dataset (MAE and \mathcal{C})
- 8: **if** $g \bmod N_{\text{opt}} = 0$ **then**
- 9: Optimize numeric literals with CMA-ES
- 10: Use $\alpha \cdot N$ samples for CMA-ES fitness calls (unless full-data final mode)
- 11: **end if**
- 12: Update f^* if a better MAE is found
- 13: Select survivors with NSGA-II in $(\text{MAE}, \mathcal{C})$
- 14: **end for**
- 15: Optionally apply final CMA-ES refinement to f^* on full data
- 16: **return** f^*

E. Implementation Details

The implementation relies on `Ministral-14B`, an LLM developed by Mistral AI [21], featuring 14 billion parameters. Structured outputs are enforced by constraining the model’s generation process with a predefined JSON schema, implemented via the `Pydantic` and the `instructor` library. This ensures compliance with the required data types and structural specifications, effectively preventing runtime parsing errors and supporting the continuity of the evolutionary cycle. All simulations were conducted on a single NVIDIA H200 Tensor Core GPU, equipped with 141 GB of high-bandwidth memory (HBM3e VRAM).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section evaluates both the capabilities and the sensitivity of the proposed framework to its main design choices. The analysis begins with a baseline configuration to provide intuition into the method’s dynamics, followed by an assessment of key hyperparameters: population size, the inclusion of numerical optimization, and the fraction of the dataset used during numerical optimization.

A. Baseline Configuration and Reference ML Models

Before analyzing the sensitivity of the proposed framework, the performance of widely used models is assessed as a reference. The selected models include Linear Regression (LR) and Decision Trees (DT) with a maximum depth between three and four. Moreover, an Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) model, with a maximum depth of four and 200 estimators, is evaluated to provide a comparison with more complex approaches. To further benchmark our proposal against an interpretable symbolic-regression method, *PySR* is also evaluated for 200 iterations, matching the evolutionary horizon used by the proposed framework. Results, presented in Table III, indicate that while LR exhibits the lowest imitation performance, it has the second lowest count of mental operations. In turn, *PySR* provides the most interpretable model with moderate predictive accuracy, while XGB achieves strong predictive accuracy at the expense of a substantially higher complexity score, driven by the large number of trees required to produce a single decision. Due to this higher complexity, XGB is excluded from further analysis.

Table III: Performance of ML-based reference models.

Model	Acronym	MAE (€/kWh)	\mathcal{C}
Linear Regression	LR	0.1086	25
Symbolic Regression	PySR	0.0870	13
Decision Tree (depth 3)	DT (d=3)	0.0738	29
Decision Tree (depth 4)	DT (d=4)	0.0617	61
Extreme Gradient Boosting	XGB	0.0383	11392

The behavior of the proposed framework is then examined under a base configuration, summarized in Table IV, which serves as a reference for the subsequent experiments. For this baseline configuration, each 200-generation run required, on average, 9,785 LLM calls and 16.49M tokens.

Table IV: Base configuration details.

Configuration	Acronym	Setting
Population size	μ	25 individuals
Generations	G	200
Numerical optimization	–	Enabled
LLM-RG temperature	T_{RG}	0.1
LLM-FB temperature	T_{FB}	0.5
Dataset fraction	α	20%
Children per survivor	–	2

Fig. 2 illustrates the evolutionary trajectory of the base configuration in the fidelity-interpretability space. The horizontal axis represents structural complexity, measured as the total number of mental operations, while the vertical axis reports MAE (how well the surrogate imitates the optimization problem). The curve depicts the trajectory of the best solution (i.e., lowest MAE) in each generation, with the color gradient indicating the progression over generations.

The results show that, as evolution progresses, candidate solutions improve gradually, with a reduction in MAE, while structural complexity stabilizes. This behavior highlights an initial exploration phase followed by a refinement stage,

where both symbolic structure and numerical parameters are progressively improved.

Notably, improvements in imitation performance are not strictly monotonic with respect to complexity. In several instances, lower MAE is achieved with comparable or even lower complexity, indicating that the framework can discover more efficient rule representations rather than simply increasing model size.

Figure 2: Performance of the base configuration.

Listing 1 showcases the best rule set, retrieved from Trial4 which returned a $MAE_{f_{base,best}}$ of 0.076 €/kWh and $\mathcal{C}(f_{base,best})$ of 23. Under this configuration, a imitation performance comparable to DT (d=3) is achieved, alongside greater interpretability, even surpassing that of LR. The rules consider *if/else* conditions related to load and RES generation, and additional linear terms and interactions that relate market prices, price elasticity, and hour, while always returning solutions within the target range.

```
def predict(features, X):
    market_load_interaction = features['Market Prices'] *
    → features['Mean (Load)']
    elasticity_term = 0.978 + (-0.515 *
    → (features['Self-elasticity'] + 0.745)) + (0.438 *
    → features['Self-elasticity'] * features['Hour'])
    elasticity_term += -0.712 * features['Market Prices']
    elasticity_term += 0.066 * market_load_interaction

    if features['Mean (Load)'] * features['Mean (RES)'] >
    → 10000.299:
        return 0.282
    elif features['Mean (Load)'] > 77.679:
        return 0.6
    else:
        return max(0.052, min(0.6, elasticity_term))
```

Listing 1: Best performing rule set with base configuration.

B. Sensitivity Analysis

Table V presents the parameter values tested in the sensitivity analysis, while Fig. 3 summarizes the behavior of the proposed scenarios in the fidelity-interpretability space. Similarly, the colored curve shows the median evolutionary trajectory of the best-performing solution under a given experimental configuration, while each shaded area represents the range of candidate solutions across trials.

Table V: Details of the sensitivity analysis.

Parameter	Tested Values
Population size	1, 12, 25, 50
Numerical optimization	Enabled, Disabled
Dataset fraction in optimization (α)	0.1, 0.2

The hyperparameter population size directly impacts the extent of structural exploration at each generation. Fig. 3 suggests that broader exploration of the symbolic search space increases the likelihood of discovering high-quality surrogate rules, as the configuration with 50 individuals yielded a candidate solution closer to DT ($d=4$), both in terms of MAE and interpretability.

Figure 3: Performance of the sensitivity analysis

Furthermore, assessing the importance of the numerical op-

timization stage is essential. As shown in Fig. 3, the framework can still reduce imitation error even when numerical optimization is disabled, indicating that the verbal reinforcement mechanism contributes to structural improvement. However, the search does not achieve the same imitation performance compared to when optimization is enabled, plateauing earlier. Therefore, while the LLM is effective in proposing meaningful symbolic structures, optimization is essential to properly calibrate numerical coefficients. This supports the hybrid design of the framework, where LLMs perform structural discovery and another optimization layer focuses on tuning coefficients.

Finally, the effect of the dataset fraction used during numerical optimization is assessed. As depicted in Fig. 3, both configurations exhibit very similar trajectories in the fidelity-interpretability space. This suggests that relatively small subsets of the dataset are sufficient to guide the optimization process effectively. Thus, this strategy provides a practical way to reduce computational cost without significantly degrading the quality of the resulting models. Moreover, it should be noted that this analysis returned an improved set of rules compared to the base configuration, depicted by Listing 2, reaching $MAE_{f_{10pc,best}} = 0.061 \text{ €/kWh}$ and $\mathcal{C}(f_{10pc,best}) = 37$, while also surpassing DT ($d=4$) in imitation performance and interpretability.

```
def predict(features, X):
    mean_res = features['Mean (RES)']
    hour = features['Hour']

    if hour < 8.932:
        return max(0.05, 1.254 - (hour * 0.128) - 0.571)
    elif mean_res + (hour * -0.078) > 124.785:
        return max(0.261, min(1.243, -0.324 + (mean_res *
        ↪ -0.182)))
    elif hour >= 14.95:
        return max(0.105, min(0.6, 2.278 + (hour - 15.039)
        ↪ * -0.277))
    else:
        return max(-0.338, min(0.374, 0.234 + (mean_res *
        ↪ 0.077 if mean_res < 49.999 else 0.117)))
```

Listing 2: Best rule set using a dataset fraction of 10%.

C. Natural Language Explanation

At this stage, the framework demonstrates that LLMs can distill a complex optimization problem into a simple, interpretable rule set with high fidelity; however, linking the resulting logic to real-world meaning remains challenging. To address this, a natural language explanation module is introduced to translate the Python rule into an audience-aware explanation. To preserve fidelity, the prompt [20] includes the original rule code, the extracted branch structure, semantic descriptions of the features, and audience-specific instructions with explicit output constraints.

Listing 3 showcases the natural language explanation based on the rule set 2 targeting EV drivers as an audience, provided by GPT-5.4 [22]. This explanation is effective not only because it translates the rule into user-understandable terms, but also because it exposes behavior that would otherwise remain opaque, such as branches that effectively collapse into

near-constant outputs due to clipping. This contributes to a more transparent account of how the rule behaves in practice.

```
{
"audience": "EV-User",
"summary": "Big takeaway: this rule mainly cares about the time of
day, with renewable supply only nudging the price around the middle
of the day. In practice, charging is usually cheapest very early in
the morning (it quickly drops to about 0.05EUR/kWh by around 5 AM),
usually mid-priced late morning to mid-afternoon (mostly around
0.35-0.37EUR/kWh), and usually most expensive from about 3 PM to 9 PM
(typically 0.60EUR/kWh). There is one exception: if renewable supply
is unusually high around late morning or early afternoon, the price
drops to a flat 0.261EUR/kWh. Very late at night, after the evening
peak, it falls again and can get down to about 0.105EUR/kWh near 11
PM. So, for a practical rule of thumb: cheapest is early morning,
worst is late afternoon/evening, and midday is usually in the middle
unless renewables are especially strong."
}
```

Listing 3: Explanation generated for EV users.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed an LLM-guided evolutionary framework to derive interpretable surrogate rules for dynamic carbon-aware EV charging tariffs, combining rule generation and feedback from two LLM instances with numerical optimization and multi-objective selection to balance predictive accuracy and structural simplicity.

By distilling the behavior of a mathematical stochastic optimization model for EV charging tariffs into compact rule-based functions, this approach offered a practical way to improve transparency of tariff design and reduce the “black-box” nature of mathematical optimization, while remaining competitive relative to conventional ML models in both accuracy and interpretability. Quantitatively, the best candidate achieved an MAE of 0.061 €/kWh with a complexity of 37, slightly outperforming DT (d=4) (0.0617, 61) and clearly improving over LR (0.1086, 25), DT (d=3) (0.0738, 29), and PySR (0.0870, 13) in imitation accuracy, although PySR remains the most compact nonlinear symbolic baseline, highlighting the framework’s favorable imitation-interpretability trade-off.

Results show that broader structural exploration improves the quality of the discovered rules, with larger populations yielding solutions closer to deeper decision trees baselines, and that verbal LLM-guided refinement alone can reduce imitation error across generations. However, it is evident that complementing this with numerical optimization significantly enhances performance.

Therefore, this work demonstrates the potential of LLMs to construct and explain interpretable surrogate models that effectively imitates the outputs of an optimization in energy applications.

However, this framework is constrained by its computational cost, mainly due to the repeated LLM inference calls required by the evolutionary search, by practical non-determinism, and susceptibility to occasional hallucinations and degenerate rules, including expressions whose apparent complexity ultimately reduces to near-constant outputs. Accordingly, the reported results should be interpreted as promising but preliminary, since current LLM inference pipelines may exhibit run-to-run variability even under zero temperature [23].

Additionally, the learned rules are dependent on the optimization and should be updated whenever relevant changes in demand, renewable generation, carbon intensity, or any other optimization-side input variable.

Finally, future work should address LLM sensitivity, including temperature and prompt robustness, alongside rule simplification, semantic validation, and more robust generation constraints to reduce hallucinated or degenerate rules and enhance the reliability of the resulting surrogate models.

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